

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(2)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 166 sahifa,
5-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – “Yangi O'zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: “Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon” MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Bitiruvchi talabalarning qadriyatlar tizimining psixologik xususiyatlari	10
<i>Abdulazizova Muslima, Abdurasulova Sevinch, Ikromova Aziza, Iskanderova Sayora</i>	
Oila va ta'lim tizimida raqamli xavfsizlik madaniyatini shakllantirish va uning psixologik omillari.....	14
<i>Nurmatov Nurhayot Nurziyot o'g'li, Yo'lchiyeva Zarinabonu Sanjarali qizi</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining o'rni	18
<i>Abdullayeva Arofatxon Abduvaxobovna, Mirzahamdov Shahriyor Botir o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarni sport musobaqalariga tayyorlashda jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetensiyasining tarkibiy tuzilmasi va rivojlanish mexanizmlari	22
<i>Abduraximov Ziyodullo Xojakbar o'g'li, Tuxtapulatov Shahobiddin Nuriddinovich, Nasimov Ulug'bek Orif o'g'li</i>	
Ta'limni raqamli transformatsiyalash sharoitida o'quv jarayonini tashkil etishning integratsion shakllarini qo'llash metodikasi.....	28
<i>Allamova Shoxista Shavkat qizi</i>	
Surxon vohasida sog'liqni saqlash tizimi: muammolar va yechimlar (Sherobod tumani misolida, 1925–1945-yillar).....	33
<i>Allamurotov Asadbek Baxtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida kasbga yo'naltirish tizimini takomillashtirish	37
<i>Axmedova Muxabbat Axmedovna</i>	
Ko'p o'zgaruvchili funktsiyaning oraliq qiymatlari haqidagi teoremlar va ularning isbotlari	42
<i>Boqiyev X. X., Muxtorova Sevinch Asad qizi, Yuldoshova E'zoza Ravshan qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak mutaxassislarining huquqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	46
<i>D. M. Xolnazarova</i>	
Oilaviy tarbiya samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar: tajriba-sinov natijalari asosida	49
<i>Ibragimova Aziza Toshniyazovna</i>	
Bo'lajak tabiiy fanlar o'qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini shakllantirishda interaktiv integratsiyaning roli	55
<i>Jo'rayeva Xushro'ya Yaxyoxon qizi</i>	
Corrective Feedback in Foreign Language Learning Acts as a Vital Tool for Improving Accuracy With Research Indicating.....	58
<i>Kamalova Dilnoza Kurbanbayevna</i>	
Doping va halollik masalasi: sportdagi dolzarb muammo.....	64
<i>Kobilov Sobir Donakulovich</i>	
Yunon-rum kurashi bilan shug'ullanuvchi sportchilarning teknik va taktik harakatlarini takomillashtirish usullari.....	69
<i>Muhtorov Abdusattor Abdupatto o'g'li</i>	
3-4 yoshli bolalarda nutqning grammatik tuzilishini shakllantirishning psixolingvistik asoslari	75
<i>Rasulova Xulkaroy Abduhalil qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda gender identifikatsiyasini rivojlantirishda ota-onalar bilan ishlashning mobil ilovaga asoslangan innovatsion modeli	80
<i>Razzoqova Mahliyo Qosimjonovna</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida geografiya fanining zamonaviy metodik yondashuvlari va o'qitishning samaradorligi.....	84
<i>Sunnatillayeva Zarina Sulaymon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligini oshirish usullari	88
<i>Usmonov Salohiddin, Jo'rayeva Rayhona</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining konfliktologik kompetentligini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi	94
<i>Latipova Ma'rifat Salohiddin qizi, Zaripova Xolida Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning interfaol metodlari.....	100
<i>Zokirov Mirzaraxim Abdualiyevich</i>	

O'quv jarayonida innovatsion baholash texnologiyalarining ilmiy-pedagogik mazmuni	103
<i>Sobirova Marjona Shavkat qizi</i>	
Taekvondochilarning musobaqa davrida hujumkorlik jihatlarini oshirish	110
<i>Abdulfattoyev Abrorjon Abduraxmon o'g'li</i>	
Gender yondashuv asosida talabalarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	114
<i>Shokirova Hilola Abduraxmon qizi</i>	
Ingliz tilida tinglab tushunish malakasini rivojlantirishda raqamli ta'limning samaradorligi	120
<i>Aytimbetova U. T.</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish...	124
<i>Axmedova Nazokat Erkinovna</i>	
"Inklyuziv ta'lim. gospital pedagogika" fanida dasturiy-metodik ta'minotning mazmuniy-texnologik va monitoring-dagnostik komponentlari.....	128
<i>Azamxonov Baxodir Sayitkamolxonovich</i>	
Ingliz tilida og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda 5–6-sinf o'quvchilari uchun samarali usullar	132
<i>Rajabova Zarafshon Davronovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishning innovatsion-metodik asoslari	135
<i>Tuxtayeva Mehriyo Shavkatovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda sifat so'z turkumini o'rganish mazmuni.....	140
<i>Usmonova Gulnoza Jaloliddin qizi</i>	
Образность современной медицинской терминологии	144
<i>Дулдулова Наргиза Ашимовна, Мирзаахмедова Нигора Ашимовна</i>	
Развитие исследовательской компетентности младших школьников посредством межпредметной проектной деятельности.....	148
<i>Мухтарова Лобар Абдиманнабовна, Нормаматова Розия Уктам кизи</i>	
Психолого-педагогические риски цифровой образовательной среды	154
<i>Рузметова Хилола Абдушариповна, Моминова Мадина Шукурулла кизи</i>	
"TALIA": система контент-генерации на основе ИИ для подготовки учителей	158
<i>Хасанов Зафар Шавкат угли</i>	

CORRECTIVE FEEDBACK IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING ACTS AS A VITAL TOOL FOR IMPROVING ACCURACY WITH RESEARCH INDICATING

Kamalova Dilnoza Kurbanbayevna

Orcid:0009-0003-2976-9251

Abstract: This article analyzes the problem of implementing corrective feedback in foreign language learning at a university as a type of feedback between teacher and student. Feedback is presented as a method of correcting student errors during assessment. The functions of feedback, its mechanism, and the stages of its implementation are discussed. The article presents the characteristics of oral and written corrective feedback, identifying and characterizing its various types and subtypes in terms of their characteristics and effectiveness. Various approaches to correcting student errors in writing and speaking are analyzed. Special attention is given to the conditions for effective feedback. Feedback is implemented in both full-time and distance learning.

Key words: foreign language, corrective feedback, oral speech, written speech, distance learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada universitetda chet tillarini o'rganishda tuzatuvchi fikr-mulohazalarni amalga oshirish muammosi o'qituvchi va talaba o'rtasidagi fikr-mulohaza turi sifatida tahlil qilinadi. Fikr-mulohaza baholash paytida talabalarning xatolarini tuzatish usuli sifatida taqdim etiladi. Fikr-mulohazaning funksiyalari, uning mexanizmi va uni amalga oshirish bosqichlari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada og'zaki va yozma tuzatuvchi fikr-mulohazalarning xususiyatlari keltirilgan, ularning turli turlari va kichik turlari ularning xususiyatlari hamda samaradorligi nuqtai nazaridan aniqlangan va tavsiflangan. Talabalarning yozma va og'zaki nutqdagi xatolarini tuzatishning turli yondashuvlari tahlil qilingan. Samarali fikr-mulohaza shartlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Fikr-mulohaza kunduzgi va masofaviy ta'limda ham amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, tuzatuvchi fikr-mulohaza, og'zaki nutq, yozma nutq, masofaviy ta'lim.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается проблема реализации корректирующей обратной связи в процессе изучения иностранных языков в университете как одной из форм взаимодействия между преподавателем и студентом. Обратная связь представлена как эффективный инструмент выявления и исправления ошибок обучающихся в ходе оценивания результатов их учебной деятельности. Анализируются функции обратной связи, механизм её действия и основные этапы реализации в образовательном процессе. В статье раскрываются особенности устной и письменной корректирующей обратной связи, определяются и характеризуются различные её виды и подвиды с точки зрения их специфики и эффективности. Рассмотрены различные подходы к исправлению ошибок в устной и письменной речи студентов. Особое внимание уделено условиям организации эффективной обратной связи, способствующей повышению качества обучения иностранным языкам. Отмечается, что корректирующая обратная связь может успешно применяться как в условиях традиционного очного обучения, так и в формате дистанционного образования.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, корректирующая обратная связь, устная речь, письменная речь, дистанционное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

The current renewal of the content and structure of education requires a fundamental rethinking of the relationship between teacher and student, specifically the reorientation of the teacher from a supervisor of educational activities, who must monitor students' knowledge acquisition, to an equal participant in this process.

In today's era of globalization, learning foreign languages has become a necessity for everyone. Knowledge of a foreign language is not only a guarantee of personal development in modern society but also a guarantee of professional success. At the same time, the correct analysis of errors made by language learners and their use as a teaching tool requires a high-level methodological approach from the teacher.

In the process of learning a language, intellectual communication, that is, communicative activity, plays a key role. When a person learning a foreign language learns a language based not on grammatical rules but

on the need to express their thoughts, the learning process becomes more effective. Mistakes are a natural part of this process, and by correcting them, the exchange of ideas becomes deeper. To feel confident in this role, the teacher must be well versed in the methods and technologies of such teaching and have tested and experienced them firsthand. Creating a favorable learning environment is impossible without feedback, which allows the teacher to regularly monitor and correct students' knowledge acquisition ^[1].

Therefore, the issues of providing corrective feedback during foreign language learning in higher education institutions (universities), effective methods for implementing it, and the correct correction of students' errors during oral and written communication remain relevant today.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The problem of providing feedback is not only pedagogical but also psychological since it concerns interpersonal communication and mutual activity. For social psychology, this is still a fairly new area of research. N.V. Amyaga et al. ^[2] argue that feedback is becoming one of the main poorly resolved problems of social psychology. Speaking about pedagogical research, it should be noted that the issue of feedback has long been considered mainly in terms of the classification of its types ^[3; 4; 5]. Thus, philologists offer a diverse typology of feedback and consider it in different contexts: teacher–student ^[6; 7], in oral or written speech ^[8; 9], and in distance learning ^[10].

Researchers pay special attention to studying the issue of students' awareness of the types of effective feedback ^[11], their awareness of the importance of its use ^[11], and also study the implementation of feedback between students ^[12]. However, despite the significant number of publications on the issue under consideration, the mechanism for implementing corrective feedback requires special attention.

The purpose of this article is to define the concept of “corrective feedback” and explore the conditions for ensuring effective corrective feedback between teacher and student during foreign language acquisition at a university by examining its functions, types, stages, methods, and implementation approaches.

The Problem of Learning Errors and Their Role in Language Teaching

An error in language learning is a sign that the learner has not fully mastered certain rules of the language system. If earlier errors were assessed as a negative phenomenon, today they are considered a positive indicator of the learning process.

According to S. Pit Corder, one of the founders of the theory of error analysis (Error Analysis), an error is evidence of learning because, through errors, the learner tries to express their thoughts in the language and thus tests new language elements.

The main task is not to eliminate the error but to actively involve the learner in the process of understanding the error and correcting it.

Communication in Learning a Foreign Language (Communicative Competence)

Communication is the learner's ability to freely express their thoughts in a foreign language, listen to the interlocutor, and conduct meaningful communication. This skill consists of the following components:

1. **Linguistic competence** – a set of grammatical and lexical knowledge.
2. **Sociocultural competence** – behavior appropriate to the communicative situation.
3. **Strategic competence** – the ability to correct an error or express an idea differently when it is noticed during communication.

In this process, the teacher should teach the student not only to follow grammatical rules but also to exchange ideas, engage in dialogue, and think freely in the language.

Methods of Error Correction

There are several types of error correction in teaching a foreign language:

3.1. Direct Correction by the Teacher

The teacher identifies the error and says or writes the correct form. This method is effective mainly at the initial stage since the student does not yet have the skills of self-control.

3.2. Indirect Correction

The teacher does not directly point out the error but, through gestures, questions, or intonation, encourages the student to find the error independently. This method activates thinking at intermediate and advanced levels.

3.3. Peer Correction

Students identify and discuss errors in each other's speech. As a result, the exchange of ideas in a communicative environment increases, and the student learns to accept criticism positively.

3.4. Self-Correction

This is the most effective form, in which the student, after expressing an opinion, identifies and corrects the error independently. The teacher plays a guiding role.

Psychological Foundations of Error Correction During Communication

The psychology of language learning shows that excessive correction reduces the student's motivation. Therefore, the process of correcting errors should always be carried out in a supportive and positive environment.

A mistake is an opportunity to learn. The student's sense of success should always be a priority in the process of expressing opinions. The teacher encourages the student to think logically by asking the question, "Why is this form an error?"

The Role of Correcting Errors in the Communicative Approach

Today's communicative methodology emphasizes that, during the lesson process, the exchange of meaningful ideas is more important than grammatical accuracy. Accordingly, the timing of error correction should also be carefully chosen.

Situation - Need to Correct? - Correction Method

1. The idea is misunderstood - Yes - Directly or indirectly.
2. A grammatical error that does not affect the content - Later analysis - Through written commentary.
3. A pronunciation error disrupts communication - Yes - Through modeling.
4. Providing evidence at the learning stage - Yes - Through mutual analysis.

Developing Language Sensitivity in the Student Through Error Correction

Understanding and eliminating an error develops language awareness, that is, the ability to observe one's own speech. The student gradually begins to ask questions such as, "Is this word correct to use?" and "Which form sounds more natural?" Then, the process of error correction becomes a tool for thinking.

At this stage, the teacher performs the following tasks:

1. Creates a humane and trusting communication environment.
2. Accepts the error as a learning tool, not an assessment.
3. Encourages the student to think independently.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Feedback plays an important role in the process of foreign language acquisition. Feedback is the primary control function (especially ongoing assessment), which ensures the management of the foreign language learning process^[6]. However, feedback is not only an indicator of student knowledge^[5]. Feedback operates in two directions: toward the teacher and toward the student. Feedback directed toward the teacher provides information about the level of student performance. The teacher analyzes information about deficiencies, monitors deviations in students' speech activity, and determines the degree to which the chosen teaching strategies and tactics meet actual needs. This makes it possible to promptly assess the methodological situation and make the necessary corrective changes in the selection of techniques, methods, and teaching approaches, the choice of exercises, the determination of the mode and duration of their implementation, and the sequence of organizing educational work with students. Feedback directed toward students provides them with information about the results of their learning activities in mastering foreign language skills and abilities^[8] (Klyaznika, 2014). Thus, students are informed about their strengths and weaknesses in the learning process^[7].

Feedback methods vary. The traditional approach involves filling out printed forms and then checking the student's work. This method is usually slow and should be avoided when immediate feedback is required. Students can ask questions of the teacher, for example, after explaining grammar material or to clarify the correct pronunciation of vocabulary items during practical lessons, and receive immediate feedback. The teacher can assign students homework to solve problem situations or complete test assignments. For students

who are active in practical lessons and complete independent work, the teacher should always select tasks that provide feedback. This method maintains student activity and interest. The easiest way to obtain feedback is through memorization of key concepts and self-assessment of knowledge. The teacher must ensure that key concepts are presented concisely and clearly. Computer programs can test students' knowledge, for example, through test questions.

The teacher selects feedback mechanisms based on student reactions. It is crucial to help students understand their role in choosing these pathways and to recognize and facilitate their implementation ^[7]. To ensure effective feedback, it is necessary to maintain a consistent organizational structure. The first stage involves assessing student performance, learning, and setting goals; the second stage involves assessment, self-assessment, and pair work; and the third stage involves student monitoring of achievements and reflection ^[6].

Effective feedback has three aspects:

1. Structure (goals, location, timing, and student orientation to the content);
2. Content (constructive and differentiated);
3. Format (oral, written, graphic, or video presentation) ^[11].

Since corrective feedback, known as error correction or grammar correction, is the primary means for a teacher to address student errors ^[12], a distinction is made between oral and written corrective feedback between the teacher and student during the learning process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Various types of oral corrective feedback are known, namely: explicit (direct), metalinguistic, and implicit (indirect) feedback, which is divided into such subtypes as paraphrasing a statement, requesting clarification, eliciting the correct answer, and repetition with emphasis on the error (repetition) ^[6].

T.E. Klets ^[6] believes that a combination of different types of oral corrective feedback is most effective, depending on the students' level of preparation, the type of learning activity, student preferences, learning styles, and many other factors.

Explicit (direct) oral feedback is characterized by a clear indication of the error and the provision of a reformulation. Explicit feedback is more effective in encouraging students to correctly apply the target structure both during lessons and in subsequent testing.

The metalinguistic oral feedback strategy involves providing students with linguistic clues for self-correcting errors. This type of feedback can be applied in three ways: metalinguistic comments, metalinguistic information, and metalinguistic questions.

Comments that merely indicate the occurrence of an error are considered the least informative. Metalinguistic information not only indicates the presence or location of an error but also offers specific metalinguistic cues that indirectly indicate its nature. Metalinguistic questions draw attention to the nature of the error while also encouraging students to reproduce this information independently. A disadvantage of metalinguistic feedback is that it may inhibit the fluency of speech.

This approach is sometimes considered a type of explicit feedback. Requests for clarification are used when the teacher is confident that the student possesses adequate linguistic abilities and encourages the student to reformulate their statement. Unlike explicit error correction or paraphrasing, requests for clarification are a more reliable means of ensuring that the student produces the corrected formulation.

Paraphrasing deserves the most attention, as it is most frequently used in teaching, although it often causes both positive and negative reactions. It is most often used for grammatical and phonetic errors. Paraphrasing provides students with the correct forms of the foreign language and, in a context that identifies the connections between form and content. Furthermore, paraphrasing does not disrupt the flow of communication, which facilitates the acquisition of linguistic and speech material. Corrective feedback facilitates student acceptance of the teacher's corrective action during form discussions, where students are encouraged to independently correct errors and are provided with clues regarding the need to correct incorrectly formulated statements. Paraphrasing is the most common method of correcting oral (grammatical and phonetic) errors, although students with low levels of proficiency do not always fully notice it. Therefore, the teacher should match paraphrasing with the students' level of linguistic competence and combine it with other types of feedback.

This may be due to the following factors: limited students' working memory, familiarization with new language material, multiple corrections, complex changes in paraphrasing, students' low level of linguistic proficiency, and the presence of new grammatical structures that the students have not yet mastered. Therefore, paraphrasing is more appropriate when working with students with a higher level of linguistic proficiency.

The goal of eliciting the correct answer from the student is to encourage them to independently correct the error. This strategy can be applied in one of three ways. In the first, the teacher asks the student to rephrase the erroneous statement; in the second, the teacher asks open-ended questions. The last option, which is the least stimulating and therefore the most implicit, involves using pauses of silence to allow the student to complete the sentence independently. This type of corrective feedback is usually not used in conjunction with other types of feedback.

Repetition involves the teacher repeating the incorrectly formulated part of the statement, usually emphasizing the error ^[6]. Corrective feedback is sometimes considered a type of negative feedback. This is because when a student makes an error, the teacher must first determine what kind of error it is, whether it should be corrected, and who should correct it ^[1].

Klets ^[6] believes that when it comes to activating speech fluency, it is best to postpone corrections until after completing speech-rate exercises, after which the task can be analyzed using one of the effective feedback strategies. However, it is advisable to correct errors immediately during exercises aimed at practicing speech accuracy.

Written corrective feedback refers to an approach to correcting student errors in written work that should be well balanced and selective for different types of errors. Various approaches are known regarding the types of feedback.

Some researchers distinguish between direct feedback, where the teacher corrects the error and writes the correct answer, and indirect feedback, which includes coding errors (spelling (SP), grammar (GR), etc.) and underlining the error so that the student can correct it independently ^[12]. Researchers ^[12] tend to believe that direct corrective feedback is divided into two types: errors corrected personally by the teacher or through the use of metalinguistic information, while indirect corrective feedback involves only student corrections that force them to think independently.

Identifying and correcting errors collaboratively with the student, combined with such activities as discussing errors in a group and individually, checking and rewriting written work after receiving comments from the teacher, mini-lessons on specific problematic issues, and keeping track of errors to develop the student's corresponding skills and abilities, have an effective impact on the development and improvement of writing skills. Indirect error detection forces students to analyze errors, delve deeper into a specific grammatical phenomenon, and, in the process, refine their editing skills, which leads to better long-term success in writing.

Peer editing is controversial. However, it is known that errors in others' work are sometimes easier to spot than in one's own. Involving students in such work generally motivates the development of their editing skills. Foreign language teaching methodology proposes a clearly structured, supervised, three-stage process in which students first examine errors in completed texts, then edit each other's work, and only then focus on editing their own work. However, teachers must develop their own feedback strategy for students' writing errors ^[8].

Today's reality requires providing feedback not only during classroom lessons but also during distance learning. Due to the introduction of pandemic restrictions for students, the educational process was organized using distance-learning technologies.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The essence of feedback is that in interpersonal communication during classroom lessons, the exchange of information is characterized by immediacy and emotion, whereas in remote communication, it occurs indirectly and virtually ^[10].

Corrective feedback during distance learning is not simply informing the student of the correctness or incorrectness of an assignment, assigning a grade, points, and so on. It should most likely include commentary with an analysis of errors and a review of the completed assignment to help the student avoid repeating the same shortcomings in their work and in completing subsequent assignments ^[10]. This type of feedback can be recommended for tasks aimed at developing or improving vocabulary and grammar skills.

Regarding detailed and personalized positive feedback on open-ended assignments, it should be noted that it has a positive impact on student motivation and engagement in distance learning. Negative feedback informs the student that their answer is incorrect. If the answer is incorrect, the correct option is not provided. Hints for the student may include, for example, links to relevant sections of a grammar reference book or supporting information on websites related to the topic.

Distance learning has become an additional form of education today, parallel to full-time instruction, and therefore independent ongoing thematic assessments and the use of additional teaching aids, textbooks, and dictionaries can be offered on a distance-learning platform. Moreover, distance learning, with its objective

advantages—flexibility, openness, interactivity, and individualization—is a cost-effective method for educational institutions.

Thus, corrective feedback is a method of correcting student errors during the assessment of knowledge, skills, and abilities in order to obtain information about the success of the completed assignment and the effectiveness of the teacher's foreign language teaching methods. It is an integral component of the methodological strategy of the educational process at a university. To summarize the above, we highlight the key factors influencing the effectiveness of student feedback as the scientific novelty of our study:

1. Teacher awareness of the types and methods of its implementation;
2. Adherence to structure;
3. Regularity of use;
4. Clarity for the student;
5. A clear connection to subsequent tasks, focusing first on learning goals and then on assessment;
6. Positive impact on the student;
7. Correcting written errors in collaboration with the student;
8. The use of paraphrasing in oral speech for students with a sufficient and advanced level of foreign language proficiency and a combination of paraphrasing with other types of corrective feedback for students with an intermediate level of proficiency;
9. Immediate correction of phonetic errors during the development and automation of pronunciation skills;
10. The provision of comments on completed tasks in distance learning;
11. A detailed and individualized approach.

The theoretical and practical significance of this study lies in examining the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms for ensuring the effectiveness of feedback with students during foreign language learning. Prospects for further scientific research should be aimed at a scientifically based analysis and selection of effective techniques, methods, and means for implementing corrective feedback at different stages of a foreign language practical lesson, in various forms and types of work, using innovative teaching technologies that foreign language teachers can apply in their professional practice.

List of References:

1. Bessonov, K.A. Feedback in the Pedagogical Interaction between Teacher and Student. *Juvenis Scientia*. 2016. No. 2. P. 86-89.
2. Amyaga, N.V., Aimautova, N.E., Onzimba Lenyungo, Z.B. Feedback in Studies of Interpersonal Interaction. *RUDN University Bulletin. Series: Sociology*. 2014. No. 3. P. 207-215.
3. Shute, V.J. Focus on Formative Feedback. *Review of Educational Research*. 2008. Vol. 78, No. 1. P. 153-189.
4. Liu, N.F., Carless, D. Peer Feedback: The Learning Element of Peer Assessment. *Teaching in Higher Education*. 2006. Vol. 11, No. 3. P. 279-290.
5. Orsmond, P., Maw, S.J., Park, J., Gomez, S., Crook, A. Moving Feedback Forward: Theory to Practice. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 2013. Vol. 38, No. 2. P. 240-252.
6. Klets, T.E. Feedback as a Means of Diagnosing the Pedagogical Results of Foreign Language Interactive Communication. *Proceedings of the Pskov Polytechnic Institute*. 2011. Vol. 1. No. 15. P. 82-87.
7. Kadyrberdieva, B.M., Khabibullaeva, N.Z. Feedback as an Effective Tool for Increasing Student Motivation in Learning English. *OshTU News*. 2018. Part 2. No. 1. P. 187-192.
8. Bredikhina, I.A. *Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages: Teaching the Basic Types of Speech Activity*. Yekaterinburg: Ural University Publishing House, 2018.
9. Blair, A., McGinty, S. Feedback Dialogues: Exploring the Student Perspective. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 2013. Vol. 38, No. 4. P. 466-476.
10. Gramma, D.V., Shukurova, I.V. Teaching Students a Foreign Language Using Distance Learning Technologies. *Pedagogical Review*. 2019. No. 3 (25). P. 151–157.
11. Kharlamenko, I.V., Vonog, V.V. Feedback as a Form of Control in a Technogenic Educational Environment. *Informatics and Education*. 2020. No. 5. P. 44-49.
12. Chen, J., Lin, J., Jian, L. Corrective Feedback in SLA: Theoretical Relevance and Empirical Research. *English Language Teaching*. 2016. Vol. 9, No. 11. P. 85-94.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.